

ing water at 40 DE by wet IC and followed by passing a wooden plank between crop rows. A randomized complete block design with three replications was used. Rainfall amounted to 1150 and 1135 mm in 75 and 79 rainy days during the cropping seasons of 1992 and 1994, respectively. The rice cultivar was Abhilash (155 d). Common weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* spp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyanotis* spp., and *Eclipta prostrata*.

The results (see table) indicated that intercropped *C. juncea*, *V. sinensis*, *G. max*, and *S. rostrata*, when combined with 1 IC at 15 DE and 1 HW at 40 DE, could suppress weeds effectively. The rice yields obtained in these plots were similar to those recorded after butachlor applications with 1 HW at 30 DE (see table), suggesting that these crops could replace butachlor application when combined with 1 IC. *Sesbania aculeata*, which grows very slowly, could not suppress weeds effectively.

Vigna sinensis had better weed-smothering ability and rice yields were comparable with those using butachlor with 1 HW at 30 DE, even when combined with 1 HW at 30 DE.

Apart from their weed-smothering ability these legumes can fix atmospheric N and add a considerable amount of organic matter to the soil. Therefore, intercropping of *C. juncea*, *V. sinensis*, *G. max*, and *S. rostrata* may be encouraged for sustainable weed management in rainfed lowland rice. ■

Research methodology

Modified method for determination of amylose content using a single rice kernel

B. R. Swain and M. Nagaraju, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India

Amylose content determines the stickiness and eating quality of cooked rice. We modified Shen's (1990) method to determine amylose content in a single rice kernel. We tested the method by analyzing 11 varieties having waxy, intermediate, and high amylose content.

The final protocol involved the following steps. A single rice kernel was milled by a hand-set miller and the embryo carefully removed with a blade. The material was weighed on an Afcoset electronic balance (0.1 mg-180 g) and placed in a 50-mL graduated tube. A total of 0.1 mL of 95% ethanol and 1.8 mL of 1 N NaOH solution was added. The mixture was kept in a hot-water bath (35 °C) for 20 h. It was shaken well and brought to 20 ml with distilled water. A 5 mL aliquot was pipetted into a 100 mL volumetric flask. One milliliter of acetic acid and 2 mL of iodine solution were added. The solution was brought to full volume with distilled water and shaken well. Color was read at 620 nm after 20 min in a UV

Amylose content of 11 varieties tested by two methods. Cuttack, India.

Genotype	Modified		Juliano	
	Amylose content	Type	Amylose content	Type
Malagkit Sungsong	3.5	Waxy	3.7	Waxy
Basmati 370	19.9	Intermediate	19.0	Intermediate
Karnal local	20.8	Intermediate	20.1	Intermediate
Basmati 113	20.8	Intermediate	20.1	Intermediate
T412	21.3	Intermediate	20.8	Intermediate
Pakistan Basmati	21.4	Intermediate	20.7	Intermediate
Sitabhog	21.4	Intermediate	20.9	Intermediate
Tulsimanjari	23.7	High	23.9	High
Savitri	24.7	High	24.9	High
Gayatri	25.2	High	26.3	High
Ratna	25.2	High	25.5	High

1201 spectrophotometer. Concentration of amylose was determined from a standard curve using amylose (Sigma).

According to the amylose content of control varieties Malagkit Sungsong (waxy), Basmati 370 (intermediate), and Ratna (high), we changed the classification of amylose to waxy (0-5), intermediate (5-17), intermediate (17-22), and high (>22). The amylose content of the 11 varieties is shown in the table. Most of them were intermediate, four were high, and one was waxy.

This method is suitable for determination of amylose content in a large number of samples for genetic studies. The results agreed closely with those obtained using Juliano's standard method. ■

Comparison of two scoring systems for evaluating stem rot resistance in rice, and a new proposed rating scale

R. Singh and D. S. Dodan, CCS, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station, Kaul 136021, Haryana, India

Genotypes judged susceptible by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES, 1988) often fall into the resistant or intermediate category when scored using the rating scale by Jackson et al (1977). The SES scale is based on disease incidence (% infected tillers) and excludes few resistant genotypes.

Jackson's scale uses disease severity and groups some genotypes as resistant. A new six-point rating scale proposed here accounts for both incidence and severity by using a coefficient of infection (CI):

Score	Reaction	Description (CI%)
0	Highly resistant	No symptoms
1	Resistant	Less than 5%
2	Moderately resistant	Above 5-10%
3	Moderately susceptible	Above 10-20%
4	Susceptible	Above 20-40%
5	Highly susceptible	Above 40%

To use this proposed rating scale, tillers are classified into Jackson's categories: 1 = no symptoms, 2 = lesions confined to outer leaf sheath, 3 = lesions extending through the leaf sheath to outer culm, 4 = lesions penetrating the culm resulting in partial rotting of the culm, 5 = mycelium and/or sclerotia formed within the culm, stem completely rotten. These categories are then assigned numerical values of 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0, respectively, to give relative weight to the tillers falling in different categories so that computed CI values do not exceed 100%. A zero value is assigned to healthy tillers instead of the 1 value used by Jackson. The formula for determining CI is similar to that given by Jackson in determining the weighted disease index except that (a) numerical values of 0 to 1 assigned to the scales of 0 to 5 are used in computations and (b) the weighted disease index so obtained is multiplied by 100 to obtain % CI.

The table shows the screening of a collection of 78 rice genotypes against stem rot by use of the three methods in 1992 and 1993. We found 4 resistant, 9 intermediate, and 65 susceptible using SES; 48 resistant, 21 intermediate, and 9 susceptible using Jackson's scale; and 10 resistant, 17 intermediate, and 51 susceptible using the new scale. Four resistant, 4 intermediate, and 45 sus-

Categorization of rice genotypes scored by different rating scales.

Reaction	SES (1988)	Jackson et al (1977)	New proposed scale
Resistant	Gobind, IR35546-17-3-1-3, KJT72-1-173-44, RYT3/13	Basmati 370, Gobind, HKR86-196, HKR86-403, HKR90-403, HKR90-408, HKR90-410, HKR90-413, HKR90-421, HKR90-424, HKR90-426, HKR91-403, HKR91-410, HKR91-417, HKR91-419, HKR91-420, HKR91-422, HKR91-423, HKR91-438, HKR91-452, HKR91-453, HKR91-455, HKR91-459, HKR91-465, HKR91-471, HKR238, Haryana Basmati No. 1, IET10918, IR9761-19-1, IR31785-58-1-2-3-3, IR35366-62-1-2-2-3, IR35546-17-3-1-3, IRON84-142, KJT72-1-173-44, NDR84, NDR85, NDR86, Pusa 33, Pusa Basmati No. 1, Ratna, RP1674-690-390-14, RP1681-170-4-204, RP2632-249-5-5, RP2633-15-2-5, RP2633-30-4-10, RYT3/13, Taraori Basmati, UPR756-2-1-3	Gond, HKR86-403, HKR90-408, HKR90-410, HKR91-438, IR35546-17-3-1-3, KJT72-1-173-44, RP2633-15-2-5, RYT3/13, Taraori Basmati
Intermediate	Basmati 370, HKR91-417, HKR91-423, HKR91-438, IET10918, IRON84-142, RP2633-15-2-5, Taraori Basmati, TNAU85-19-79	HKR86-1, HKR86-217, HKR90-407, HKR91-405, HKR91-458, HKR91-462, HKR91-464, HKR91-468, HKR91-470, IRON86-171, KAU8754, KAU8759, KAU8770, KAU8772, NDR118, RP2235-113-35-20, RP2434-17-9-5, RP2632-334-2-5, RP2633-30-4-7, RP2633-110-11-2, RP2633-225-10-8	Basmati 370, HKR90-403, HKR90-421, HKR91-403, HKR91-417, HKR91-422, HKR238, IET10918, IR9761-19-1, IRON84-142, NDR84, NDR85, Pusa 33, Ratna, RP1681-170-4-204, RP2632-249-5-5, UPR756-2-1-3
Susceptible	AS26556, BK779-50, Haryana Basmati No. 1, HKR86-1, HKR86-196, HKR86-217, HKR9-403, HKR90-407, HKR90-408, HKR90-410, HKR90-413, HKR90-421, HKR9-424, HKR90-426, HKR91-403, HKR91-405, HKR91-410, HKR91-419, HKR91-420, HKR91-423, HKR91-424, HKR91-452, HKR91-453, HKR91-455, HKR91-458, HKR91-459, HKR91-462, HKR91-464, HKR91-465, HKR91-468, HKR91-470, HKR91-471, HKR238, IR9761-19-1, IR31785-58-1-2-2-3, IR35366-62-1-2-2-3, IRON86-171, KAU8754, KAU8759, KAU8770, KAU8772, MTU7991, NDR84, NDR85, NDR86, NDR118, NLR33055, Pusa Basmati No. 1, Pusa 33, Pusa 834-13-101, Pusa 835-5-2-101, Ratna, RP1674-690-390-14, RP1681-170-4-204, RP2235-113-35-20, RP2434-17-7-5, RP2632-249-5-5, RP2632-334-2-5, RP2633-30-4-7, RP2633-110-11-2, RP2633-67-7-9, RP2633-110-11-2, RP2633-225-10-8, TNAU851979, UPR756-2-1-3	AS26556, BK779-50, HKR91-424, MTU7991, NLR33055, Pusa 834-13-101, Pusa 835-5-2-101, RP2633-67-7-9, TNAU851979	AS26556, HKR86-1, HKR86-196, HKR86-217, HKR90-407, HKR90-413, HKR90-424, HKR90-426, HKR91-405, HKR91-410, HKR91-419, HKR91-420, HKR91-423, HKR91-424, HKR91-452, HKR91-453, HKR91-455, HKR91-458, HKR91-459, HKR91-462, HKR91-464, HKR91-465, HKR91-468, HKR91-470, HKR91-471, Haryana Basmati No. 1, IR1674-690-390-14, IR31785-58-1-2-3-3, IR35366-62-1-2-2-3, IRON86-171, KAU8754, KAU8759, KAU8770, KAU8772, MTU7991, NDR86, NDR118, NLR33055, Pusa 834-13-101, Pusa 835-5-2-101, Pusa Basmati No. 1, RP2235-113-35-20, RP2434-17-9-5, RP2632-334-2-5, RP2633-30-4-7, RP2633-110-11-2, RP2633-225-10-8, TNAU851979

ceptible genotypes were found in common between the new scale and SES. Ten resistant, no intermediate, and 8 susceptible genotypes were in common between the SES scale and Jackson's scale. Six genotypes (HKR86-403, HKR90-408, HKR90-410, HKR91-438,

RP2633-15-2-5, and Taraori Basmati) found resistant with the new scale had 7.4, 10.0, 9.1, 7.4, 5.3, and 7.3% of infected tillers. These entries were excluded from the resistant category by SES because they just crossed the resistance limit (<5% infected tillers). ■

removed 7 d after oviposition and kept in a container for hatching. The larvae can either be used for experiments or for reinfesting a fresh plot to maintain the colony.

Four separate, overlapping colonies can be maintained by infesting every 4th plot with larvae from a single earlier plot. Alternatively, because moth emergence from each plot occurs over a period of 12-18 d, colonies can be continuously mixed by infesting each new plot with larvae from 2-3 previous plots.

Between August 1994 and January 1996, we reared 4 separate, overlapping YSB colonies for 6-10 generations each, assuring an uninterrupted supply of 200-600 female moths each week. The overall mean number of moths produced and sex ratio (proportion of females among total adults) were 865.1 ± 11.5 and 0.57 ± 0.001 , respectively. Mean developmental time was 39.2 ± 0.04 d and was highly dependent upon seasonal temperatures. Colony performance was measured by total number of moths produced and the sex ratio. The table shows that performance was not correlated with the number of generations a colony had been in culture, indicating that colony performance did not deteriorate over time. In 3 of the 4 colonies, performance was not correlated with age of plants at the time of infestation (range 65-100 d after sowing), indicating that reproductive-stage plants of a wide range of ages were suitable for colony maintenance. ■

A procedure for continuous greenhouse rearing of the yellow stem borer

L. M. Sunio, J. S. Bentur, and M. B. Cohen, IIRRI

Studies of yellow stem borer (YSB), *Scirpophaga incertulas*, are often disrupted because of the great difficulty of rearing this species. We have developed a procedure to maintain colonies of YSB in a greenhouse. This procedure has provided us with a daily supply of adults for our research.

Our greenhouse has a floor space of 56×20 m. The planting area is divided into 16 plots of 15 m^2 . Seedlings of rice variety IR62 are grown and transplanted in each of the plots at 7- to 10-d intervals. Each plot has 11 rows of 32 hills planted at 20×20 -cm spacing. To initiate colonies, adult moths of YSB are collected from the field and caged on plants for oviposition. Neonate larvae hatch from these egg masses and are used to infest the plots at 10-15 larvae hill⁻¹ when the plants are 65-100 d old. At this stage of plant growth, each hill

has 12-15 tillers and 4224 tillers are infested in each plot. Four weeks after infestation, the plants are trimmed 40 cm above ground level to facilitate adult moth emergence. Plots of trimmed plants are covered with fine fiberglass mesh to collect adults. Moths are collected every day and caged on 40-d-old potted plants for oviposition. Pieces of leaves with egg masses are

Performance of YSB colonies at IIRRI over time.^a

Colony	Dependent variable	
	Sex ratio	Total adults produced
Colony A (n = 6 generations)		
Generation	0.510	-0.307
Plant age	-0.004	0.119
Colony B1 (n = 10)		
Generation	0.413	-0.364
Plant age	0.896 ^b	0.427
Colony B2 (n = 7)		
Generation	0.903	0.711
Plant age	0.606	0.552
Colony C (n = 8)		
Generation	0.212	-0.329
Plant age	0.260	0.644

^aValues are correlation coefficients. ^bSignificant (P<0.05).

Herbicides in Asian rice: transitions in weed management

EDITED BY R. NAYLOR

270 pages. 1996. 15.24 x 22.86 cm. Paperback. HDC US\$20.00; LDC US\$5.00 plus airmail (US\$12.00) or surface mail (US\$5.00) postage.

Weeds have been a persistent problem in rice since the beginning of settled agriculture. For Asia as a whole, weeds cause an estimated 10-15% reduction in rice yields — equivalent to about 50 million tons of rough rice annually.

The papers in this book define the links between the economics of weed control, herbicide use, and weed ecology. The presentations provide a basis for developing a much broader array of weed management tools from which integrated weed management strategies can be designed. Understanding the linkages and developing rational methods are critical in efforts to achieve greater sustainability of rice production.

Asian rice bowls: the returning crisis?

P. L. PINGALI, M. HOSSAIN, AND R. V. GERPACIO

341 pages. 1997. 15.24 x 22.86 cm. Paperback. HDC: Send your order to CAB International, Wallingford, Oxon OX10 8DE, United Kingdom; LDC US\$ 18.00 plus airmail (US\$22.00) or surface mail (US\$9.00) postage.

Less than two decades ago, the world was focusing on the impending food crisis across Asia, which was given little hope of ever being able to meet its rapidly growing food demand. Since then, Asia has made a quantum leap in food production. Technological innovations and policies that promoted rice production systems helped achieve this.

The authors argue that there is a growing sense of complacency about future food supplies in Asia and that such complacency is not warranted. While rice productivity may increase, this will be limited by a number of factors: withdrawal of land and labor from agriculture to other uses, increased competition for resources, and land degradation. It is unlikely to match the increase in demand for rice because of population growth.

This book provides a thorough assessment of the opportunities for increasing land productivity, including crop diversification. It evaluates the successes and limitations of the Green Revolution for rice in Asia and projects economic and technological trends forward over the next three decades. Overall, it provides a major synthesis of interest to academics and professionals in a wide range of disciplines, including crop science, development studies, agricultural policy, and agricultural and food economics.

Rice almanac

INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE

181 pages. 1997. 17.78 x 25.40 cm. Paperback. HDC US\$13.00; LDC US\$3.50 plus airmail (US\$12.00) or surface mail (US\$5.00) postage.

The Rice Almanac was first published in 1993 in response to the long-felt need to bring together general information about rice—its origin and diffusion, its growth and production, the ecosystem under which it is grown, and opportunities for increased yields. Demand for the Almanac was so strong that the 1st edition of 5,000 copies was sold out some time ago.

This 2nd edition contains updated material on the production and geographical data presented in the 1st edition plus new information for a number of African countries as well as regional information on West Africa, Latin America and Caribbean, and European rice production.

An electronic version of the Almanac has also been prepared and is available on the Internet at <<http://www.riceweb.org>>. At this site, regular updates and additions will be made and coverage of the Almanac expanded.